

Nazarin Kamannin Sauti: Bakaken Hausa Masu Kugiya a Bakin Yarbawa Mazauna Garin Gusau

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Tsakure: *Fannin kamannin Sauti fanni ne da ke lura da yadda sautin magana ke tafiya daga bakin wanda ya furta zuwa ga mai sauraro. Don haka fanni ne da ke kalailaice igiyar silalin sauti tare da awon amo da karajin sauti da kuma tsawon lokacin da sautin ke dauka a lokacin da aka furta shi. Bugu da kari, yana fayyace maginan sauti (Formants) da ke kunshe cikin kowace kwayar sauti da aka furta. Ana kuma nuna kadadar sauti ta amfani da na'urar taswirar sauti (Soundwave and Spectrogram). Kasancewar kowane harshe da nasa tsarin sauti, wannan ya sa ake jin wasu Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau na furta bakaken Hausa masu kugiya ba daidai ba. An yi amfani da manhajar Praat wajen kalailaice aiki, an kuma nadi muryar masu bayar da bayani shida, maza uku mata uku. Binciken ya gano cewa Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau ba sa iya furta bakaken /b/, da /d/, da /y/ sukan musanyan su da /b/, da /d/, da /y/. Wannan kuma bai rasa nasaba da rashin wadancan kwayoyin a harshen Yarbanci. Bugu da kari, an gano cewa suna iya furta bakin /k/ da kyau. An yi la'akari da wannan ta hanyar kalailaice kamannin sautin kowane baki daga cikin jerin kalmomin da ke dauke da bakake masu kugiya wadanda masu bayar da bayani suka furta.*

Gabatarwa

Harshen Hausa yana daya daga cikin rukunin Harsunan Chadi, shi kuma harshen Yarbanci yana a rukunin harsunan Niger-Congo (Greenberg, 1966). Duk da haka, akwai alaƙa tsakanin waɗannan harsuna ta hulɗar kasuwanci, da zamantakewa da auratayya da kaurace-kaurace da makarantun boko da Islamiya da aikin gwamnati da sauransu. Hakan ya sa, dole ne majiya harsunan biyu su yi koƙarin koyan harsunan juna. Kowane harshe da nasa tsarin sautin, don haka, harshen Hausa yana da wasu bakake da ake kira masu kugiya ko lanƙwasa wanda harshen Yarbanci ba shi da irinsu. A mu'amala ta yau da kullum akan ji wasu Yarbawa a garin Gusau suna furta waɗannan bakake ba daidai ba. Alal misali, sautin /b/ wanda ke da ƙungiya sukan musanya shi da sautin /b/ marar kugiya wanda suke da shi a nasu tsarin sautin. Wannan bincike ya yi amfani da ilimin kimiyyar harsuna na gwaje-gwaje, domin tabbatar da abin da ake hasashe a kimiyyance.

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Manufar Bincike

Manufar wannan bincike ita ce kara fahimtar yadda ‘yan asalin wani harshe Yarbawa waƙanda ba Hausawa ba, ke furta bakafake masu kugiya na Hausa. Wannan bincike yana da kudurori kamar haka:

- i. Nazartar bambancin da yake faruwa wurin furucin bakafake masu kugiya a bakin Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau.
- ii. Gano yadda furucin bakafaken Hausa masu kugiya yake a bakin Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau.
- iii. Tantance kadadar bakafaken Hausa masu kugiya a bakin Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau.

Kadadar Bincike

Wannan binciken ya takaita ne ga iyakacin Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau. Bincike ne da ya kalli kabilar Yarbawa da kuma bakafake masu kugiya kadai, ba tare sauran bakafaken ba.

Bitar Ayyukan da Suka Gabata

Fitattun masana ilimin kimiyyar harsuna kamar Ferdinand de Saussure (1916) da Leonard Bloomfield (1933) da Noam Chomsky (1957) da William Labov (1963) da Steven Pinker (1994) da Syal and Jindal (2007) sun bayyana ilimin kimiyyar harsuna a matsayin fagen ilimin da ke nazartar harsuna a kimiyyance. Wannan fage yana da manyan rassa daban-daban, ilimin furuci da ilimin tsarin sauti sun shafi sautukan magana ne wato baki ko wasali, yayin da ilimin tasarifi da na ginin jimla suka shafi kalmomi, sai kuma ilimin ma’ana da ya shafi nazarin ma’ana.

Ilimin Furuci da na Tsarin Sauti ginshikai ne na rassan Ilimin Harsuna waƙanda ke nazarta abubuwan da suka shafi sautin magana. Sani (2010, sh. 1), ya bayyana ma’anar furuci da cewa “Aiwatar da sautin magana ne ko zance tare da taimakon wasu sassan jiki da ake kira mafurta da kuma sarrafa iska”. A wani kaulin cewa ya yi : Ilimin Furuci reshe ne na Ilimin Harsuna wanda ake siffanta sautukan magana na ɗan’adam ta yadda ake furta su da yadda ake kamanta su da kuma yadda ake jin su. Sani (2011:2) Wato dai furuci ba zai yiwu ba sai da gabobin furuci da kuma zirin iska. Ilimin furuci kuwa, fanni ne na ilimin kimiyyar harshe wanda ya shafi nazarin yadda ake samar da sautukan magana na harshe, musamman waƙanda ake samun bayanansu da rabe-rabensu, (Crystal 2008:363). Shi kuwa Osisánwó (2009:22) cewa ya yi, “Yin amfani da alamu na musamman, wani lokaci daban da harufa, wajen wakiltar sautukan magana”. Hakazalika, masana irin su Peter Ladefoged (2006), da Victoria Fromkin (2000) da Kenneth N. Stevens (2002), da John Laver (1994) da Catford, P.C. (1977) da Sani (2010 da 2015) sun ce akwai hanyoyi uku mabambanta da ake bi wajen bayyana sautukan magana na kowane harshe kamar haka:

- I. **Fannin Furta Sauti:** wannan fagen nazarin sautukan magana na harshe ya shafi yadda ake samar da sautukan magana na harshe ta yin la’akari da abubuwa guda biyu da ake kira gabobin furuci da kuma zirin iska.
- II. **Fannin jin Sauti:** wannan fage ne da ya shafi yadda ake tantance sautukan magana na harshe ta hanyar ji da kunne.

III. **Fannin kamannin Sauti:** wannan fage ya shafi nazarin sauti ta la'akari da mai furta sautin da kuma mai saurarensa.

Fannin kamannin Sauti: Fanni ne da ke lura da yadda sautin magana ke tafiya daga bakin wanda ya furta zuwa ga mai sauraro. Don haka fanni ne da ke kalailaice igiyar silalin sauti tare da awon amo da karajin sauti da kuma tsawon lokacin da sautin ke dauka a lokacin da aka furta shi. Bugu da kari, yana fayyace maginan sauti (Formants) da ke kunshe cikin kowace kwayar sauti da aka furta. Ana kuma nuna kadadar sauti ta amfani da na'urar taswirar sauti (Soundwave and Spectrogram). Ana kamanta tsananin amon kowane sauti da aka furta. Don haka, ilimin fannin kamannin sauti, ilimi ne da ke bayyana kadadar kowane sauti a zahirance tare da kididdige da kalailaice nauyinsa da karajinsa.

Akwai na'urorin gwaje-gwajen sauti da suka jibanci kowane fanni daga cikin fannoni uku da aka ambata, misali, a fannin furta sauti ana amfani da na'urar gwajen makwallato, wato Electromyography, da kuma na'urar gwajin ganda a lokacin furta wani sautin magana wato, Electropalatography (EPG), a fannin jin sauti ma, ana amfani da na'urar tantance alakar kwakwalwa da jin sauti wato Electroencephalography (EEG), a fannin kamannin Sauti, kafin zuwa fasahar zamani ta karni na ashirin da daya ana amfani da na'urorin bayyana taswirar sauti, kamar na'urar Kay Sonagraph, wadda ke nuna kadadar sautuka (Ladefoged, 1975, p. 123).

Hoto na 1: Na'urar Kay Sonagraph

Madogara: Kafar Intanet: www.google.com/search?q=Kay+Sonagraph+image

Har wa yau akan yi amfani da rediyo irin na gargajiya wurin nadar murya ta amfani da kaset domin gudanar da binciken kamannin sautuka (Crystal, 1987, p. 234).

Hoto na 2: Rediyon Gargajiya

Madogara: Kafar Intanet: <https://www.shutterstock.com/image-photo/retro-outdated-cassette-tape>

Ma'aunin taguwar sauti kuwa (**Oscilloscopes**), ana amfani da shi domin wajen baje taguwar sauti tare da nuna karajin sauti da kuma mita (Fromkin et al., 1989, p. 298).

Hoto na 3: Ma'aunin Taguwar Sauti (**Oscilloscopes**),

Madogara: Kafar Intanet: <https://reamstime.com/vintage-oscilloscope-retro-electrical-device-generative>

Bugu da kari, akwai, mitar kalailaice Sauti **Frequency Analyzers**, wanda ake auna kayayyakin da ke kunshe cikin kowane sauti (Kent, 1983, p. 156).

Hoto na 4: Mitar kalailaice Sauti **Frequency Analyzers**

Madogara: Kafar Intanet: <http://www.sglabs.it/en/product.php?s=anritsu-wiltron-ms710e&id=1323>

A wannan zamani na fasahar dijital, ana amfani da na'urar kalailaice sauti kamar, Praat da Audacity (Martin-Rubió, 2021), Kasancewar waƙannan na'urorin gwaje-gwajen sauti a fannoni ukun suna da tsada, ba a cika samun su a dāƙunan gwaje-gwajen kimiyyar harsuna a mafi yawan manyan makarantun kasashe masu tasowa ba. Hakan, ya sa ba a yi rubuce-rubuce masu yawa ba a fannin kamannin sauti na harshen Hausa ta amfani da hanyar gwaje-gwajen sauti a kimiyyance. Fasahar sadarwa ta zamani ta karni na 21 ta saukaƙa yanayin gudanar da irin wannan bincike. An samar da manhajoji da saftuwayoyi da kayayyakin aikin gwaje-gwaje mabambanta a kowane fanni. Akwai waƙanda ake saya ta intanet akwai kuma waƙanda aka samar kyauta domin koyo da koyarwa da kara faɗaɗa bincike a fannin kimiyyar gwaje-gwajen sauti.

A fannin kamanni sauti, masana ilimin furuci da na tsarin sautin Hausa sun fara cin gajiyar wannan fasaha ta karni na 21. Manazarta irinsu (Jamilu, 2018) da Maimuna (2019) da Abdullah (2019) da kuma Umar (2024) duka sun gudanar da bincike a kan fannin kamannin sauti na harshen Hausa ta amfani da na'urar *Praat* (Boersma & Weenink, 2018).

Dabarun Bincike

Tsarin bincike da farko dai an fara da karance-karancen litattafai da maƙalu da kundayen bincike da kamusu da ke da alaƙa da ilimin tsarin furuci da ilimin tsarin sauti. An fi mayar da hankali ga waƙanda suka shafi fannin kamanta sauti. An saurari laccoci kuma an kalli bidiyo da ke koyar da makamar sanin fannin kamanta sauti waƙanda aka saukar ta kafar Youtube. Waƙannan abubuwa da aka nazarta su suka share fagen samun makama da madafar gudanar da wannan binciken.

Masu ba da bayanai: A tsarin gabatar da bincike na fannin kamanta sauti ana buƙatar masu ba da bayanai domin samun ingantaccen sakamako. Ladefoged (1993, sh. 67).

An yi amfani da Tambayau Game Da Tasirin Harshen Uwa a Kan Harshe Na Biyu (LBQ) wajen tantance masu ba da bayani. Dukkan masu ba da bayani asalin Yarbawa ne, suna amfani da harshen Hausa a harkokin yau da kullum.

Don haka an zaɓi Yarbawa shida (6) a matsayin masu ba da bayanai waƙanda shekarun su yake tsakanin shekera talatin zuwa arba'in (30-40), an zaɓi maza uku, mata uku, an kuma tabbatar da cewa masu ba da bayanai ba su dāuke da wata lalura rashin (lafiya) lalurar kwaƙwalwa ko ta wurin furta magana ko jin sautin murya, kuma sun kasance Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau a jihar Zamfara. An ba kowane mai ba da bayani takardar neman izinin shiga wannan binciken.

Kayan Aikin Tattara Bayanai:- Kasancewar wannan aiki yana da alaƙa da kimiyyar gwaje-gwajen sauti, an yi amfani da na'urori da dākin gwaje-gwajen sauti da kayayyakin naɗar murya ingantattu.

Naɗar Murya (Rikodin): An yi amfani da na'urar Audacity, wannan manhajar tana da inganci wajen naɗar murya da kuma tace sauti. An yi amfani da dākin gwaje-gwajen kimiyyar harsuna da ke Jami'ar tarayya ta Gusau wajen kalailaice muryoyin da aka naɗa ta amfani da kwamfuta da kuma manhajar Audacity.

Na'urar Kalailaice Kamannin Sauti: Domin samun nasarar wannan binciken an yi amfani da na'urar kalailaice kamannin sauti Praat wadda Pau Boerma da David weemnk, waƙanda ke cibiyar kimiyyar ilimin furuci da ilimin tsarin sauti da ke jami'ar Amsterdam a shekarar 1991. Bugu da

kari sun ci gaba da kula da ita da sabunta ta har zuwa yau ana amfani da wannan manhajar Praat wajen kalailaice kamannin sauti ta hanyar hoton kadadar sauti, kalailaice maginin sauti da awon amon sauti da awon lokacin da sauti ke duka kafin a furta shi da kuma awon karajin sauti. Ana iya saukar da wannan manhaja kyauta a likau: https://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/download_win.html.

Masana da manazarta ilimin furuci da ilimin tsarin sauti suna amfani da wannan manhajar a sassan duniya baki daya domin ana samunta a intanet kyauta kuma an tabbatar da inganci da sahihanci da sakamakon da take bayarwa.

Ingancin Kayan Aikin Tattara Bayanai: Ingancin kayan aiki ya zama tamkar ruhin gudanar da sahihi kuma karbabben bincike. Don haka an yi kwarya-kwaryar gwajin na dukkanin na'urorin da aka ambata a sama domin samun tabbacin ingancinsu don haka dukkanin kayayyakin da aka yi amfani da su masu inganci ne.

Jerin Kalmomin Bincike: Domin cimma manufar wannan bincike na gano kamannin sautin bakafen Hausa masu kugiya a bakin Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau, an zaɓo kalmomi da ake amfani da su yau da kullum waɗanda ke duka da baƙaƙe masu kugiya a farkon kalma ko tsakiyar kalma ko karshe kuma duka kalmomin ne na asali ba na aro ba ana samun masu gaba biyu da masu gaba uku kamar yadda yake a kasa:

Jadawali na 1: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike

Lamba	Bakake Masu Kugiya	Rubutun Sauti	Rubutun Yau Da Kullum	Ma'ana da Ingilishi
1	/b/	/bàra:wò:/	Barawo	Theif
2	/b/	/be:ra:/	Bera	Mouse
3	/b/	/ba:ɸ /	Baci	Insult
4	/d/	/dà:kii/	Daki	Room
5	/d/	/dàri:/	Dari	Hundred
6	/d/	/daja/	Daya	One
7	/k/	/ka:tò:/	Kato	Huge
8	/k/	/karɸi:/	Karfi	Strength
9	/k/	/kàrami:/	Karami	Small
10	/ʔj/	/ʔjamma:ta:/	‘Yammata	Girls
11	/ʔj/	/ʔjanɸi:/	‘Yanci	Freedom
12	/ʔj/	/ʔja:ʔja:/	‘Ya’ya	Children

Kalailaice Kamannin Sautin Bakaken Hausa Masu Kugiya a Bakin Yarbawa Mazauna Gusau

An gabatar da gundarin aiki tare da kalailaice dukkan kalmomin da aka naɗo aka kuma ɗora kalmomin a manhajar PRAAT inda aka yanko baƙaƙe masu kugiya daga kalmomin da aka yi amfani da su sannan aka samar da taswirar kowane baki mai kugiya tare da bayyana kadadar kowane sauti domin gano kamannin kowane baki. An gabatar da kalailaicewa ne tare da nuna giraf da hotuna domin ganin zahirin kowane baki mai kugiya daga bakin masu bayar da bayanai maza da mata.

Hoto na 5: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike daga MBBM001

Madogara: An ɗauko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na nuna jerin kalmomin bincike da aka ɗora a kan manhajar PRAAT domin fara yanko kowace kalma da kuma yanko kowane baki daga cikin baƙaƙe masu kugiya da aka naɗo daga mai bayar da bayani mace ta ɗaya.

Hoto na 6: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike daga MBBM002

Madogara: An ɗauko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na nuna jerin kalmomin bincike da aka ɗora a kan manhajar PRAAT domin fara yanko kowace kalma da kuma yanko kowane baki daga cikin baƙaƙe masu kugiya da aka naɗo daga mai bayar da bayani mace ta biyu.

Hoto 3: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike daga MBBM003

Madogara: An dawko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na nuna jerin kalmomin bincike da aka dora a kan manhajar PRAAT domin fara yanko kowace kalma da kuma yanko kowane baki daga cikin bakake masu kugiya da aka nado daga mai bayar da bayani mace ta uku.

Hoto na 7: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike daga MBBN001

Madogara: An dawko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na nuna jerin kalmomin bincike da aka dora a kan manhajar PRAAT domin fara yanko kowace kalma da kuma yanko kowane baki daga cikin bakake masu kugiya da aka nado daga mai bayar da bayani namiji na daya.

Hoto na 8: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike daga MBBN002

Madogara: An dawko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na nuna jerin kalmomin bincike da aka dora a kan manhajar PRAAT domin fara yanko kowace kalma da kuma yanko kowane baki daga cikin baƙaƙe masu kugiya da aka nado daga mai bayar da bayani namiji na biyu.

Hoto na 9: Jerin Kalmomin Bincike daga MBBN003

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na nuna jerin kalmomin bincike da aka dora a kan manhajar PRAAT domin fara yanko kowace kalma da kuma yanko kowane baki daga cikin baƙaƙe masu kugiya da aka nado daga mai bayar da bayani namiji na uku.

4.2 Balebe, Haɗiyau, Mai-Ziza [b]

Ana kiran wannan baki balebe ne saboda wurin furucinsa labba ne ke haɗuwa wuri dāya inda leben kasa da na sama ke haɗuwa sai su samar da wannan sauti. A rubutun sauti ana zana shi kamar haka /b/. Amma a rubutun yau da kullum akan yi masa lanƙwasa ne kamar haka, babban harafi: **B** karamin harafi kuma **b**. A bangaren yanayin furucinsa kuwa, haɗiyau ne saboda yanayin furucinsa ya shafi iskar maƙwallato ziri ciki, yayin da mafurta suke haɗe, sannan suka ware, zirin iskar yakan yi kasa ne ya faɗa kasan kwararon magana. Wannan bakin mai ziza.

Hoto na 10: Furtattar Kalmar *barawo* daga MBBMN001

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na bayyana taguwar sauti da kadadar sauti da kuma taswirar sauti a matakin kwayar sauti da kalma. Layin da ke tsaye na nuna kaifin amon sauti yayin da layin da ke kwance ke nuna tsawon lokacin da aka dāuka wajen furta kalmar *barawo*.

Hoto na 11: Taswirar Kalmar barawo daga MBBN001

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton ya bayyana taswirar kalamar barawo da kuma yadda aka yanko kwayar sautin [6]

Hoto na 12: Taswirar kwayar sautin [6] daga MBBN001

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kwayar sautin /6/ daga Mai Bayar da Bayani na dāya Bayarabe, namiji. Idan aka dubi taswirar sautin, za a ga akwai rauni wajen haɗiye zirin iskar da ke biyo ta kwararon magana. Wannan hoton ya nuna an furta wannan sauti ta hanyar datse iska sannan aka sake ta, ta bi ta kwararon magana tare da wani tartsatsi irin na yanayin furucin dān lebe, tsayau mai ziza [6]

Hoto na 13: Kadadar sautin [6] daga MBBN001

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kadadar sautin ya tabbatar da abin da ka bayyan a taswirar sauti kamar yadda ake gani. Sautin a ɗan datse shi, sannan aka saki iska ta fita da ɗan kara da ke nuna yanayin furucin kwayar sautin [b].

4.3 Naɗe Harshe, Hadiyau, Mai-ziza [d]

Naɗe-harshe wurin furucinsa inda tsinin harshe ya kusanci tsinin hanka ko ya haɗe da shi. Hadiyau ne saboda yanayin furucinsa iskar maƙwallato ziri ciki, yayin da mafurta suke haɗe, sannan suka ware, zirin iskar yakan yi kasa ne ya faɗa kasan kwararon magana kuma mai ziza ne. A rubutun sauti ana zana shi kamar haka /d/. Amma a rubutun yau da kullum akan yi masa lankwasa ne kamar haka, babban harafi: 'D' karamin harafi kuma d.

Hoto na 14: Furtattar kalmar ɗaki daga MBBM001

Madogara: An ɗauko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na bayyana taguwar sauti da kadadar sauti da kuma taswirar sauti a matakin kwayar sauti da kalma. Layin da ke tsaye na nuna kaifin amon sauti yayin da layin da ke kwance ke nuna tsawon lokacin da ka ɗauka wajen furta kalmar ɗaki.

Hoto na 15: Taswirar Kalmar ɗaki daga MBBM001

Madogara: An ɗauko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton ya bayyana taswirar kalamar ɗaki da kuma yadda aka yanko kwayar sautin [d].

Hoto na 16: Taswirar kwayar sautin [d] daga MBBM001

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kwayar sautin [d] daga Mai Bayar da Bayani Mace ta dāya, Idan aka dubi taswirar sautin, za a ga an yi amfani da zirin isakar huhu mai faɗawa ciki ne a maimakon zirin iskar maƙwalloto mai faɗawa ciki, wannan ne ya haifar da sakin iskar huhun a hankali bayan an dān datse ta. Don haka kamanin sauti bahanke tsayau mai ziza [d] aka furta ba naɗe harshe haɗiyau mai ziza ba [d].

Hoto na 17: Kadadar sautin [d] daga MBBM001

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kadadar sautin ya tabbatar da abin da ka bayyan a taswirar sauti kamar yadda ake gani. Sautin an yi amfani da iskar huhu kuma aka dān dakatar da iska sannan ta sauka kasa wanda ke nuni da yanayin furucin kwayar sautin [d].

4.4: Bahandē, Tunkudau, Maras Ziza [k]

Abun da ya sa ake ce masa bahandē saboda wurin furucinsa harshe zai kusanci hanka ko ya haɗe da ita. Tunkudau yanayin furucinsa iskar maƙwallato ziri waje lokacin da mafurta suka haɗe sannan suka ware, iskar kan fice ne. Wannan sauti maras ziza ne. A rubutun sauti ana zana shi kamar haka /k/. Amma a rubutun yau da kullum akan yi masa lanƙwasa ne kamar haka, babban harafi: K karamin harafi kuma k.

Hoto na 18: Furtattar kalmar kato daga MBBN002

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na bayyana taguwar sauti da kadadar sauti da kuma taswirar sauti a matakin kwayar sauti da kalma. Layin da ke tsaye na nuna kaifin amon sauti yayin da layin da ke kwance ke nuna tsawon lokacin da ka dāuka wajen furta kalmar kato.

Hoto na 19: Taswirar Kalmar kato daga MBBN002

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton ya bayyana taswirar kalamar kato da kuma yadda aka yanko kwayar sautin [k]

Hoto na 20: Taswirar kwayar sautin [k] daga MBBN002

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kwayar sautin [k̄] daga Mai Bayar da Bayani Namiji na Biyu. Idan aka dubi taswirar sautin za a ga alamar rashin ziza sannan kuma iskar ta fice ta maƙwallato ne. Wannan ke nuna cewa kamannin sautin bakin [k̄] ne.

Hoto na 21: Kadadar sautin [k̄] daga MBBN002

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kadadar sautin ya tabbatar da abin da ka bayyan a taswirar sauti kamar yadda ake gani.

4.5 Gandantacciyar Hamza, Tsayau [ʔj]

Wurin furucinsa ana samun gamin gambiza na abu biyu: gaban harshe da ganda tsattsaura suka kusanci juna, ko suka haɗe, da kuma tantanin maƙwallato ya ja ya rage faɗin maƙwallaton.

Yanayin furucinsa iskar huhu ziri waje, mafurta mai motsi da maras motsi sukan toshe mafitar zirin iskar a wasu wurare na ɗan lokaci kaɗan kafin su ware, zirin iskar ya fice sa saurin gaske da wata ‘yar ƙara kamar ta fitar harsashi. A rubutun sauti ana zana shi kamar haka /ʔj/. Amma a rubutun yau da kullum akan yi masa lanƙwasa ne kamar haka, babban harafi: ‘Y ƙaramin harafi kuma ‘y.

Hoto na 22: Furtattar kalmar ‘ya’ya daga MBBN003

Madogara: An dāuko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Hoto na sama na bayyana taguwar sauti da kadadar sauti da kuma taswirar sauti a matakin kwayar sauti da kalma. Layin da ke tsaye na nuna kaifin amon sauti yayin da layin da ke kwance ke nuna tsawon lokacin da ka dauka wajen furta kalmar ‘ya’ya.

Hoto20 : Taswirar Kalmar ‘ya’ya daga MBBN003

Wannan hoton ya bayyana taswirar kalamar ‘ya’ya da kuma yadda aka yanko kwayar sautin [ʔj]

Hoto na 23: Taswirar kwayar sautin [ʔj] daga MBBN003

Wannan hoton kwayar sautin /ʔj/ daga Mai Bayar da Bayani Namiji na Uku,i. Idan aka dubi taswirar sautin za a ga yanayin furucin ya fi kama da na bagandē kusantau mai ziza [j]

Hoto na 24: Kwayar Kadadar sautin /k/ daga MBBN003

Madogara: An dauko wannan hoton a farfajiyar PRAAT, 1/7/2024

Wannan hoton kadadar sautin ya tabbatar da abin da ka bayyana a taswirar sauti kamar yadda ake gani.

Kammalawa

Wannan bincike ya shafi nazarin kamannin sauti wanda yake nazarin kimiyyar sauti a zahirance, an yi amfani da masu bayar da bayani tare da na dayar murya, sannan aka yi amfani da manhajar Praat domin kalailaice aikin. An gamo cewa bakaken Hausa masu kugiya suna da wuyar furtawa a bakin Yarbawa mazauna garin Gusau. Sukan musanya bakin /b/ balebe hadiya mai-ziza da bakin /b/ balebe tsayau mai-ziza. Duk da yake wadannan bakake tarayya da juna a wurin furuci da matsayin maƙwallato sai dai sun bambanta a yanayin furuci. Haka kuma, an gano cewa suna iya furta bakin /k/ Bahandɛ Tunkudau Maras Ziza. An gano cewa bakin /ʔj/ gandantacciyar hamza tana da wuyar furtawa a bakinsu, kadadar sauti ya nuna bakin /j/ Bagandɛ kinin wasali mai-ziza suke furtawa.

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